

Survey of Persistent Identifier Usage in Latin American Journals in the Latindex 2.0 Catalog

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Abstract:

This study surveys the use of persistent identifiers in Latin American journals listed in the Latindex 2.0 Catalog. The countries surveyed include: Argentina, Bolivia, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Cuba, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras, Mexico, Nicaragua, Panama, Paraguay, Peru, Puerto Rico, Uruguay, and Venezuela.

Keywords: Open Access, ARK, DOAJ, DOI, Handle, Persistent Identifiers, Latindex.

Persistent Identifiers

Persistent identifiers are codes that uniquely identify a digital object. In the context of scientific and academic journals, these identifiers are used to pinpoint the publication of the object. They ensure access to the digital object via a link that remains functional beyond the status of the site hosting the journal. The most widely used persistent identifiers are DOI, HANDLE, and ARK, with the first two being proprietary and the ARK being open access.

The fundamental characteristic of persistent identifiers, as defined by Bermès (2006), is uniqueness. The first of these characteristics is uniqueness, which assumes that the identifier represents only one resource. However, the same resource, even if located in different places, should retain the same identifier. Thus, we are talking about a “globally unique” identifier, which may imply a more organized or less centralized system on an international scale (p.17).

This uniqueness means that different identifiers cannot coexist for the same digital object, i.e., the same article could not, for example, have both a DOI and an ARK. In fact, this practice promotes the preservation of the object. In the context of Open Science ecosystems, defined by UNESCO (2022) as “a set of principles and practices aimed at making scientific research in all fields accessible to everyone for the benefit of scientists and society as a whole,” having free persistent identifiers becomes an essential resource to

ensure scientific production is made available and preserved. Specifically, in Latin America, considering public funding for scientific communication in contrast to the global North model financed by commercial publishers, it is necessary in our region to have identifiers that do not depend on foreign currency payments for maintenance.

Latindex 2.0 Catalog

The Latindex 2.0 Catalog is a database comprising open-access journals that meet a series of high editorial quality criteria. To be included in this database, journals must comply with various characteristics, such as continuous content generation, a peer review system, an ethics code, and digital preservation policies. The methodology includes 38 characteristics (7 of which are considered mandatory core requirements). Journals must meet at least 30 characteristics to be included in the Latindex 2.0 Catalog.

Methodology

The data presented in this report was collected from the publicly available advanced search feature on the Latindex portal, provided in CSV format. The total number of Latin American journals in the Latindex 2.0 Catalog was searched and compared with the subset of those that meet the criterion 36 "Use of Unique Resource Identifiers (URI)." The online search was performed on October 21, 2024.

Table 1

Country	Journals	with PIDs	without PIDs	% without PIDs
Argentina	518	271	247	47%
Bolivia	12	8	4	33%
Brasil	355	293	62	17%
Chile	207	179	28	13%
Colombia	132	127	5	3%
Costa Rica	99	79	20	20%
Cuba	78	4	74	94%
Ecuador	300	202	98	32%

El Salvador	14	6	8	57%
Guatemala	22	13	9	40%
Honduras	11	11	0	0%
Mexico	371	267	104	28%
Nicaragua	20	18	2	10%
Panama	38	33	5	13%
Paraguay	21	14	7	33%
Peru	234	210	24	10%
Puerto Rico	10	3	7	70%
Dominican Republic	16	11	5	31%
Uruguay	51	47	4	7%
Venezuela	32	15	17	53%
TOTAL	2541	1811	730	28%

Source: Authors

Results

Figure 1

Uso de PID sobre las 2541 revistas Latinoamericanas que conforman el catálogo 2.0 de Latindex

Source: Authors

This report aligns with the one conducted in 2023 (Authier), based on data from the DOAJ database (<https://doaj.org/>) and complements it. The previous report showed that as of that date, 54% of the surveyed Latin American scientific journals did not have any persistent identifier. It is important to note that the Handle (<https://handle.net/>) has been in existence since 1994, and the DOI (<https://www.doi.org/>) since 1997. Currently, several countries cannot access the DOI (due to U.S. embargoes), as the DOI organization is based in the U.S. Countries such as Cuba and Iran are affected by this. Crossref is the most recognized DOI application, although other agencies exist. Crossref is a citation service that allows researchers to directly link a reference to its original content on another publisher's platform. One significant advantage of the DOI system for publishers is its ability to facilitate citation tracking, which enables content usage statistics to be collected and analyzed. This strengthens researchers' dependency on DOIs (Okunei & Chan 2023).

We opted to download and analyze data from Latindex (<https://www.latindex.org/latindex/inicio>) because of its broader coverage within Latin America. The data was filtered to exclude information on journals from Portugal, Spain, and Ibero-American journals from Asia, Europe, Eurasia, Oceania, and North America. The DOAJ report included 3,298 journals, a higher number than the 2,541 in this report. However, it is worth noting that the Latindex 2.0 Catalog requires journals to meet high-quality standards for inclusion. Only journals included in the Latindex 2.0 Catalog were surveyed.

In Argentina, out of 518 journals included in Latindex, 247 do not have any persistent identifiers as of October 21, 2024, representing 47%. Cuba shows 94% of its journals without identifiers. Brazil includes 355 journals in the Latindex 2.0 Catalog, of which 62 lack persistent identifiers, making up only 17%. The percentages by country vary widely but remain high, similar to those found in the DOAJ survey. One could argue that the implementation of a national resolver, as exists in Argentina (<http://id.caicyt.gov.ar/issn/>), which provides persistent identifiers for over 100 journals, could mitigate the lack of identifiers in those cases.

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